

Hybrid Provision of Energy based on Reliability and Resiliency by Integration of Dc Equipment

Work Package WP4

Grid planning and operation strategies

Deliverable D4.7

Effect of harmonic firewall investigated and verified

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List of Abbreviations

AC	Alternating Current
AC/DC	Alternating Current - Direct Current
AFE	Active Front End
CPL	Constant Power Load
DAB	Dual-Active Bridge
DC	Direct Current
DC/DC	Direct Current - Direct Current
EV	Electric Vehicle
FRT	Fault-Ride-Through
ICC	Instantaneous Current Control
LVDC	Low-Voltage Direct Current
MVDC	Medium-Voltage Direct Current
MV/LV	Medium-Voltage - Low-Voltage
NPC	Neutral-Point-Clamped
RES	Renewable Energy Sources
SPS	Single-Phase-Shift
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

Within hybrid Alternating Current - Direct Current (AC/DC) systems, different sources of instabilities and harmonic oscillations can be present, especially in multi-terminal, multi-vendor systems. These effects manifest themselves in oscillatory or instable behavior of bus voltage and current. They can be caused by converter controls, for example due to constant power loads or other control loop interactions. Others are caused by the interconnection of converters and insufficient consideration of resonances during system design, especially in the case of multi-vendor systems. To provide stable, safe and resilient operation, harmonic oscillations or instabilities should not propagate through a hybrid AC/DC system. Therefore, this deliverable investigates the effect of harmonic firewall in the context of hybrid AC/DC systems.

An analytical investigation of the root causes of harmonic oscillations and instabilities is provided in this report. A conclusion of this analysis is that during system design, system stability and protection scheme issues need to be considered together, because both are influenced by cable and Direct Current (DC) link parameters. The underlying trends related to system and converter parameters are presented.

Afterwards, the transfer characteristics of galvanically isolated Direct Current - Direct Current (DC/DC) converters are investigated. The effects of different control schemes are considered. The analysis is carried out in relation to the HYPERRIDE Aachen demosite. Oscillations due to voltage quality issues are well damped by the Dual-Active Bridge (DAB) under feedforward control, supplying a voltage source type load. If the converter's output is loaded by a constant current or power source, voltage quality issues do not transfer from the primary to the secondary side if the DC link capacitances are sufficiently sized and properly designed control loops are employed.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This document is a report of the activities within Task 4.7 of Work Package (WP) 4 in HYPERRIDE. The results and accomplishments on the effect of harmonic firewall are presented and explained.

1.2 Structure of the Document

This document is organised as follows: Section 1 provides information about the report content and introduces the topic of harmonic firewall in the context of hybrid AC/DC grids. Section 2 presents the employed modeling of power electronic converters and Section 3 investigates potential causes of instability. The effect of harmonic firewall is investigated in Section 4. The deliverable is concluded in Section 5.

1.3 Stability of Hybrid AC/DC Systems

Declared goal within HYPERRIDE is the increase of Technology Readiness Level (TRL) of DC technologies to enable hybrid AC/DC grids, integrating renewable energy sources in a efficient, modular and resilient way. Such hybrid systems relying on power electronics may very well constitute multi-vendor systems in their implementation. Especially power electronic converters may not be specifically designed for operation with the other converters within the system, but instead are designed for a more general set of specifications and operating conditions. Therefore, the general investigation of harmonic oscillations, resonances, voltage quality issues and their propagation through DC systems is of interest for the implementation of hybrid AC/DC grids. Focus of this deliverable is their propagation across galvanically isolated DC/DC converters. It is investigated whether such converters can act as a harmonic firewall, damping or even eliminating the aforementioned oscillations and instabilities. The investigated converters are modeled, in order to understand the causes of potential instabilities. Afterwards, the propagation of instabilities across galvanically isolated converters is analyzed. In order to relate the results to the practical aspects of HYPERRIDE, the converters and systems in this deliverable are based on the demosite in Aachen.

Figure 1: Simplified schematic of a lumped element cable model.

2 System Modeling

To investigate the stability of power electronic systems, the employed converter topologies to be investigated need to be modeled. Switched models of the converters of the HYPERRIDE Aachen demosite have been created in Task/Deliverable 3.11 (Karsten & Hu, 2022). These models serve as the basis for the time-series simulations presented in this deliverable. Furthermore, impedance considerations in the frequency domain are conducted with the help of the switched converter models.

2.1 Cables

Different cables are required for the interconnection of power electronic converters and other electrical equipment. The type of cable as well as its length determine the cable's influence on system behavior and stability. If the length L of the cable is short compared to the wavelength λ of the oscillatory phenomena that are of interest, i.e. $L \ll \lambda$, it is sufficient to model the cable with lumped RLC elements, as shown in Figure 1. This is usually the case for the interconnection of converters that are in close proximity to each other, e.g. converters that are located in the same room or building. A series resistance R_{cable} results from the limited cross-sectional area of the cable. Depending on the loop between a conductor and its return conductor, a series inductance L_{cable} results. The capacitances C_{cable1} and C_{cable2} follow from the capacitive coupling between two conductors. All of these characteristic values can commonly be determined for a given type of cable and installation, and scale with the length of the cable. As the wavelength of transients or oscillations approaches the length of the cable or is smaller, the cable has to be modeled as a transmission line. Previous work compares different cable models for the analysis of propagation of oscillations along dc power cables (Qawasmi, 2021). Where required, sufficiently precise models with distributed elements should be used to model high frequency oscillations along long cables.

2.2 Protection Equipment

Different approaches for the protection of Low-Voltage Direct Current (LVDC) and Medium-Voltage Direct Current (MVDC) systems have been presented and discussed in literature (Qawasmi, 2021; Warmuz, 2024; Hu, Stieneker, Joebges, & De Doncker, 2018). The use of DAB converters can enable the breakerless operation of a DC system (Hu, Stieneker, et al., 2018; Mencher, Mathé, & de Doncker, 2024), assuming all other components in the DC grid are able to withstand this fault handling technique. In this case, faults can be ridden through by the DAB by employing a Fault-Ride-Through (FRT) modulation (Hu, Stieneker, et al., 2018). A defined fault current can be fed into the system by the DAB to locate the fault.

The functionality of DC circuit breakers has been demonstrated and discussed as a further

Figure 2: Simplified schematic of three-phase DAB converter.

protection approach for DC systems (Qawasmi, 2021; Warmuz, 2024; Hátsági, Bergquist, Nee, Granath, & Modeer, 2024; Hátsági, Nee, Norrga, & Modeer, 2021). Such breakers can be purely semiconductor based or hybrid circuit based, consisting of semiconductors and mechanical switches. Depending on the implementation and the system's requirements additional inductances connected in series to the circuit breaker can be necessary to limit the rate of current rise in a fault case (Hátsági et al., 2024, 2021). These inductances can influence the system's stability, similarly to a cable as their inductance can be significant. They can be modeled as lumped elements (cf. Figure 1) and need to be considered in the analysis of the overall system's resonances and stability. Within HYPERRIDE MVDC hybrid circuit breaker concepts are investigated and being demonstrated (Hátsági et al., 2024, 2021; Norga et al., 2022), with ongoing work in WP 3 and WP 7.

2.3 Dual Active Bridge Converter

The HYPERRIDE Aachen demosite relies on DAB converters to couple different DC grid segments and provide galvanic isolation at the same time. Therefore, the DAB is chosen in this deliverable to be investigated as galvanically isolated DC/DC converter, especially in regard to the effect of harmonic firewall. Figure 2 shows the schematic of the investigated converter topology. It is assumed that the converter is operated under Single-Phase-Shift (SPS) modulation. For an operating range of $0 \leq \varphi \leq \frac{\pi}{3}$ the transferred power equates to (1), with the dynamic voltage ratio d and angular switching frequency ω_{sw} (cf. (2) and (3)) (De Doncker, Divan, & Kheraluwala, 1988).

$$P_{DAB} = \frac{V_{in}^2 d}{\omega_{sw} L_{\sigma}} \varphi \left(\frac{2}{3} - \frac{\varphi}{2\pi} \right) \quad (1)$$

$$d = \frac{V_{out} N_T}{V_{in}} \quad (2)$$

$$\omega_{sw} = 2\pi f_{sw} \quad (3)$$

The modeling depth of the switched converter model being used is explained in the following. This explanation aims to provide an understanding of which effects can be modeled and which can not be modeled. The switching processes of all power electronic switches are ideal and instantaneous, meaning that no switching transients are modeled. This assumption is based on the premise that the switching times are short compared to the switching period duration. While information about the switching transients is thereby lost, the execution time of the model can however be significantly faster. Nevertheless, dead-time effects can still be considered as well as semiconductor losses including switching losses. Additionally, the converter model is as

Figure 3: Single-phase equivalent circuit of transformer model.

Figure 4: Single-phase equivalent circuit of simplified transformer model.

a consequence not limited to a given choice of semiconductor technology (i.e. switch type and semiconductor technology). On-state resistances and voltages can be included in the converter model to model non-ideal conduction behavior.

Figure 3 shows the single-phase equivalent circuit of the medium-frequency transformer model employed in the switched simulation models. It consists of the series winding resistances R_1 and R_2 , stray inductances $L_{\sigma 1}$ and $L_{\sigma 2}$, magnetizing inductance L_m and an ideal transformer with the winding ratio N_T . The core losses are not of relevance for the considered stability investigations and therefore not modeled. For the given investigations, a simplified model according to Figure 4 is used. It omits the winding resistances and assumes a winding ratio of 1.

Figure 5: Modeling of the interconnection of two converters through a cable.

3 Causes of Instabilities

In this section potential causes of instabilities in hybrid AC/DC systems are explored and investigated, based on the previously presented models. Their relevance to the HYPERRIDE Aachen demosite is explained with selected examples. Further insights regarding the demosite and its operation can be gained from the deliverables of WP 7.

3.1 Cable and DC Link Resonance

The selection of a suitable cable for the interconnection of hybrid AC/DC grid segments or converters is mainly based on operating and maximum values of voltages and currents and required mode of installation (e.g. underground, in air). Further application specific requirements can also have an influence on cable selection. As explained in Section 2.1, parasitic characteristics follow from the choice of cable type and installation, which are linearly proportional to the cable length.

As a first application case, the interconnection of two converters within close proximity to one another is analyzed. Due to the short cable length in the given case, the cable can be represented by lumped inductive, resistive and capacitive elements. Figure 5 shows the schematic layout of the setup with the two converters. The converters' DC link capacitances are considered to be much greater than the parasitic capacitance of the cable, due to the short cable length. Therefore, the parasitic capacitance is neglected. The converters' inner current loop behavior is approximated by ideal current sources in this example. Based on the passive elements of the circuit, not considering the converters' impedances, a resonant circuit is formed. Its resonance frequency depends on the inductance value of the cable and the DC link capacitances, according to (4). Only the series resistance of the cable provides damping in this resonant circuit. Load steps, caused by highly dynamic converter controls or faults, can trigger this resonance.

$$\omega_{\text{res}} = \sqrt{\frac{C_{\text{out}} + C_{\text{in}}}{C_{\text{out}} C_{\text{in}} L_{\text{cable}}}} \quad (4)$$

Figure 6: Ideal CPL behavior of a converter.

3.2 Constant Power Load Behavior

In different application cases, such as Electric Vehicle (EV) charging, electrolysis, coupling of grid nodes, integration of Renewable Energy Sources (RES), a constant power transfer is desired, rather than a voltage control. The timeframe in which the power to be transferred changes is considered much greater than the time constants that determine system stability and behavior. Thereby, converters in these applications constitute a Constant Power Load (CPL). Their behavior is described by Figure 6, assuming an infinite bandwidth. A decrease of the load's input voltage V leads to an increase of its input current I (cf. (5)). P_0 describes the large-signal operating point of the converter, i.e. the power setpoint given by the application. If the characteristic is linearized in a given operating point, the rate of change of I over V is determined according to (6). This phase shift of 180° between voltage and current corresponds to a negative resistance behavior of the load, according to (7).

$$I = \frac{P_0}{V} \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dI}{dV} = -\frac{P_0}{V^2} \quad (6)$$

$$R_{\text{CPL}} = -\frac{V^2}{P_0} \quad (7)$$

The ideal CPL behavior by itself can therefore destabilize converter systems by introducing negative resistance. In the following the system resulting from interfacing a CPL through a cable is analyzed.

3.3 Constant Power Load Interfaced through a Cable

If a CPL is interfaced by a short cable (cf. Section 2.1), the circuit can be modeled by the schematic shown in Fig. 7. Employing circuit analysis, the bus admittance, seen at the connection points of the circuit, results to (8). Relating to the HYPERRIDE Aachen demosite,

Figure 7: Simplified representation of a CPL interfaced by a cable.

Parameter	Value
DC link capacitance C	5 mF
Series inductance L	30 μ H
Series resistance R	2 m Ω
CPL equivalent resistance R_{CPL}	-2.56 Ω

Table 1: System Parameters During for Evaluation

especially the case of a short cable is of interest, representing the interconnection of converters in close vicinity, e.g. in a hybrid AC/DC substation. In that case, it can be assumed that $R \approx 0$, simplifying the bus admittance to (9). At the same time, this assumption represents the worst case of no damping provided by the cable. The resonance frequency and damping of (9) are given by (10) and (11).

$$Y_{bus} = \frac{1 + j\omega R_{CPL}C}{R + R_{CPL} + j\omega(R_{CPL}RC + L) - \omega^2 R_{CPL}LC} \quad (8)$$

$$Y_{bus,simple} = \frac{1 + j\omega R_{CPL}C}{R_{CPL} + j\omega L - \omega^2 R_{CPL}LC} \quad (9)$$

$$f_0 = \frac{1}{2\pi\sqrt{LC}} \quad (10)$$

$$D = \frac{1}{2R_{CPL}} \sqrt{\frac{L}{C}} \quad (11)$$

The effects of the CPL, cable parameters and DC link sizing on the investigated system can be analyzed with (9)-(11). The equivalent CPL resistance in the given operating point leads to a negative damping factor, since R_{CPL} is negative in all cases. A short cable, with low inductance leads to a greater damping factor and an increased resonance frequency. In an application, the DC link capacitance C can be increased to increase the damping of the system. Higher values of capacitance therefore have a stabilizing effect on the system.

The system's behavior is analyzed in the following for cases in which the cable resistance is not negligible. Figure 8 shows the poles of (8), for the value of the cable inductance L varied from 10% to 100% of its nominal value given in Table 1. The pole migration under varying capacitance C and varying resistance R is shown in Figure 9 and 10. The capacitance is varied from 50% to 250% of its nominal value and the resistance is varied from 10% to 100%. Similar to the simplified system (9), an increase in cable inductance leads to a migration of the poles towards the border of the unit circle, destabilizing the system. A stabilizing effect is observed by increasing the load's DC link capacitance. Any cable resistance increases the system's damping, leading to a migration of the poles towards the center of the unit circle.

Figure 8: Dependence of the system's poles on the cable inductance.

Figure 9: Dependence of the system's poles on the DC link capacitance.

Figure 10: Dependence of the system's poles on the cable resistance.

Figure 11: Schematic representation of a DAB operated as a CPL, interfaced by a cable.

Figure 12: CPL input voltage and current for a negligible series resistance.

Figure 13: CPL input voltage and current for a series resistance of $2 \text{ m}\Omega$.

In the following, an application example is investigated, based on time-series simulations. The CPL is modeled by a DAB converter, interfaced through a cable to an 800 V DC bus, as described previously and shown in Figure 11. The bus is fed by an ideal voltage source. First, the cable resistance is set to be zero. For the cable inductance, a value of $30 \mu\text{H}$ is assumed. The converter is operated with a feedforward based power control, as described in the deliverable of WP 3.11 (Karsten & Hu, 2022). The DAB's input voltage and current are shown in Figure 12. At $t = -0.1 \text{ s}$ the converter power setpoint is 200 kW, changing to 500 kW at $t = 0$. Significant oscillations of the voltage and current are observed. This behavior corresponds to the decrease of the system's damping factor as described by (11), resulting from the increased power transfer. The oscillation's frequency matches the previously determined system's natural frequency, in this case 410.94 Hz (cf. (10)). If the cable resistance is assumed to be $2 \text{ m}\Omega$, the

voltage and current are more strongly damped, as shown in Figure 13. The amplitude of the oscillations is very limited and exponentially decaying. The system returns to a steady-state afterwards.

It is concluded that during the setup of a converter interfaced system, the influence of cable and DC link resonances and especially CPL behavior have to be considered. Care has to be taken that the resulting system is sufficiently damped. An increase of the DC link capacitance can effectively stabilize the system. Furthermore, the control of converters should be designed to either avoid CPL behavior, or to effectively limit the negative resistance behavior. The investigated systems are the basic causes of harmonic oscillations in DC systems.

It is clear from these observations, that the stability assessment of a hybrid grid is linked to the design and assessment of its protection schemes. Especially the sizing of DC link capacitors plays an important role in DC protection coordination, as it directly influences short-circuit currents and stored energy. Similarly, DC protection schemes that rely on a minimum series inductance to limit the rising rate of short-circuit currents, directly influence the system's stability, by potentially introducing additional series inductances between converters. Therefore, during system design and planning, these protection and stability aspects have to be investigated together, in order to find feasible system parameters, allowing dynamic, stable and cost effective operation of the system.

4 Harmonic Firewall

This section investigates to what extent a galvanically isolated converter can act as a harmonic firewall. It is analyzed how harmonic oscillations propagate across galvanically isolated DC/DC converters, specifically the DAB. As analyzed previously, hybrid AC/DC systems can be subjected to oscillations due to instabilities. The presence of voltage quality issues on one of the system's busses should ideally not propagate across the overall system, potentially adversely affecting control loops, stability and loads. The disturbance transfer characteristics of the DAB are investigated in Section 4.2. The application of the DAB in different application cases is investigated in Section 4.3.

4.1 Impedance Modeling

The assessment of an AC/DC system's stability, especially if it consists of multiple converters, can be conducted using the principle of passivity (Riccobono & Santi, 2012). Passivity is achieved if the total bus impedance of the system has a phase Φ fulfilling the condition $-90^\circ < \Phi < 90^\circ$, and does not have any right half plane poles. The application of passivity and similar approaches to determine system stability requires the knowledge of the investigated converter's input or output impedance, depending on the operating case. Similarly, for an adequate assessment of a converter's disturbance transfer characteristics, the transfer behavior should rather be analyzed in the frequency domain than for singular frequencies. In general, a converter's impedance behavior is in parts determined by the topology's inherent switching and modulation characteristics. This part can not be influenced by adjustments of the control loop, but only by changes of the modulation, passive components or topology. At lower frequencies, which lie within the controllable range of the converter, the control loop governs the converter's impedance behavior.

The impedance behavior can be determined experimentally for a given converter or based

Parameter	Value
Input voltage	800 V
Output voltage	800 V
Switching frequency	10 kHz
Input and output capacitance	2 mF
Series inductance	25 μ H

Table 2: Evaluation Parameters

Figure 14: Schematic of the test circuit to evaluate the propagation of oscillations.

on models specific to the employed topology. In this deliverable, time-series simulations are employed. Analytical impedance models of different converter topologies have been derived and verified in literature (Hu, An, Cui, Averous, & De Doncker, 2018; Lu, Wang, & Blaabjerg, 2019).

4.2 Dual-Active Bridge Transfer Characteristics

First, the disturbance propagation across a non-regulated DAB operating under constant phase-shift is investigated to understand the basic underlying relationships. The DAB is therefore modeled with a lossless, non-saturable transformer, as shown in Fig. 4. The parameters listed in Table 2 are used for this analysis, relating to the HYPERRIDE Aachen demosite's LVDC bus. A sinusoidal disturbance with a peak to peak amplitude of 10% of the nominal input voltage is applied to the input of the DAB. The investigated circuit is shown in Fig. 14. Applying ideal voltage sources to supply the large signal operating point on the input and output side, decouples the analysis from potential non-ideal source and load behavior.

The converter behavior is shown in Fig. 15 for an exemplary disturbance frequency of 1 kHz, resulting from a time-series simulation. The DC link voltage perturbation is modulated onto the Alternating Current (AC) waveforms, with a clear relationship between DC link voltage and AC phase to starpoint voltages. The AC phase currents' perturbation follows from the modulation of the DC perturbation onto the series inductances. Demodulation on the DAB's secondary side translates the original DC input voltage perturbation into a DC output current disturbance. It can be seen from Fig. 16 that the output current consists of a superposition of different frequencies. The Fourier spectrum of the output current is shown in Fig. 17. The output current's spectrum in the same operating point, with no input voltage perturbation of the DAB is also shown. It is observed that the input perturbation is partly translated to a disturbance component of the same frequency as the perturbation, and partly to disturbance components symmetrical around the sixth harmonic of the switching frequency. These components are found at frequencies $f = 6f_{sw} \pm f_p$. This behavior results from the modulation and switching characteristics of the converter.

Figure 15: Time-series plot of AC quantities under normal operation followed by perturbation.

Figure 16: Time-series plot of DC current under perturbation (top) and under normal operation (bottom).

Figure 17: Frequency components of the DAB's DC current under normal operation and under perturbation.

Under ideal conditions with no perturbations, the output current consists of a DC component and a ripple component, at the sixth harmonic in the case of a three-phase DAB, and at integer multiples of the sixth harmonic. The load impedance in a practical application influences the converter's output spectrum further, but is here decoupled from the analysis due to the employed ideal voltage sources. Therefore, also the DC link capacitors do not influence the disturbance transfer behavior of the converter in this analysis.

As explained in Section 4.1 for the DAB's impedance behavior, the influence of the perturbation across a bandwidth of frequencies is of interest, rather than for singular frequencies. Thereby, the primary to secondary side transfer admittance $Y_{tf} = \frac{i_s}{v_p}$ is analyzed in the following for different parameters and operating cases that are of relevance to the HYPERRIDE demosite.

The transfer admittance is plotted in Fig. 18 for the case of direct phase-shift control as assumed in the previous time-series simulation. For frequencies up to 10 kHz a constant damping of approximately 15 dB and phase of 0° are observed. A resonance occurs at the switching frequency. This resonance results from modulation of the perturbation at its own frequency onto the AC link. Non-ideal behavior such as dead-times, losses and saturation of magnetic

Figure 18: Disturbance transfer admittance Y_{tf} of DAB under direct phase-shift control.

components can make this resonance less pronounced in a real converter. A second, smaller peak of the magnitude and a correspondingly steep change of the phase are present in the vicinity of the sixth harmonic of the switching frequency. Overall, adjustments of the switching frequency lead to a shift of the admittance along the x-axis.

The influence of the series inductance on the disturbance transfer characteristic is analyzed in Fig. 19. The shown transfer admittances result from changing the series inductance to $0.5 \cdot L_{\sigma}$ and $1.5 \cdot L_{\sigma}$, while maintaining the same transferred power. The changing series inductance causes a shift of the converter's operating point. A notable difference between the three systems is only visible in the resonance behavior. The Q factor of the resonance changes as reflected by phase and magnitude. It is observed from the magnitudes and phases of the three systems, that the influence of the DAB's operating point on its disturbance transfer characteristic is not significant under the given assumptions.

Figure 19: Disturbance transfer admittance Y_{tf} of DAB under direct phase-shift control with varying series inductance.

Figure 20: Disturbance transfer admittance Y_{tf} of DAB under feedforward control, direct phase-shift control and PI control.

4.3 Application Cases

The control structure of a converter greatly influences its impedance behavior, as described in Section 4.1. At the same time, the influence of the interconnection of multiple converters must be considered, to analyze harmonic propagation properly in hybrid AC/DC systems. This includes the cables' behavior as well as converter impedances. Application cases, related to the HYPERRIDE Aachen demosite are presented in the following, considering the aforementioned aspects.

First, the DAB is controlled employing a feedforward control structure and Instantaneous Current Control (ICC) as described in the deliverable of WP 3.11 (Karsten & Hu, 2022). In this case, the reference phase-shift required for a given reference current or power is determined, depending on the input and output voltages. It is evident, that perturbations of the converter's voltages are considered in the control structure. Limitations of ideal disturbance decoupling arise from deviations of the series inductance from its assumed value, and the time-discrete nature of the control implementation. The ICC scheme allows to instantaneously set the DAB's phase currents within half of the switching period, without any oscillations. If the feedforward control is executed at twice the switching frequency, a corresponding bandwidth limitation follows for the decoupling of input voltage disturbances (Karsten & Hu, 2022).

The resulting disturbance transfer admittance Y_{tf} is plotted in Fig. 20, together with the case of operation under constant phase-shift and operation using a PI controller. An improved damping of the transferred disturbances is visible with the employed feedforward control scheme, especially at lower frequencies. The magnitudes of the admittances of the feedforward controlled converter and the converter operated under constant phase-shift are equal around 20 kHz. At higher frequencies, the transfer behavior is determined by the resonance inherent to the con-

Figure 21: Schematic of the test circuit to evaluate the propagation of oscillations under constant load current.

verter's switching behavior, and therefore equal among all three variants.

It is observed that the application of a PI control structure, without a parallel feedforward control path provides less damping of disturbances from the DAB's primary to secondary side. Below 20 Hz in the given case, it provides greater damping however than the direct, constant phase-shift control. Between 20 Hz and 20 kHz the PI controlled DAB provides approximately 1.5 dB of additional damping compared to the direct phase-shift control.

In application cases where the load of the converter can not be represented by a voltage source, the assumption of a current source, equivalent resistance or power source is valid. Therefore, the converter needs to operate under voltage control to regulate the load's voltage. Furthermore, the converter's output capacitance is no longer negligible since the load is no longer assumed to be a voltage source. Thus, the propagation of disturbances across the DAB is analyzed for operation under voltage control in the following. The simplified circuit representation of this case is shown in Fig. 21. The converter parameters in Table 2 are used for this analysis. The disturbance transfer function $\frac{V_2(\omega)}{v_p(\omega)}$ resulting from the analysis is shown in Fig. 22. A strong damping of the input voltage perturbation is observed for the output voltage transfer behavior. Thereby, voltage quality issues do not propagate across the DAB to its load side. It has to be considered however, that under the given assumption of an ideal current source load, the output capacitance is subjected to an increased ripple current, filtering the current disturbance that was investigated previously. Therefore, depending on the converter's passive components' ratings, operation under input voltage disturbances should be limited to an extent or need to be considered in DC link sizing. The output capacitance is varied to 10% and 1000% of its nominal value of 2.2 mF to visualize the influence of the output capacitance on the transfer behavior. The effect of the output capacitance on the transfer behavior is clearly visible from the bode diagram. Greater values of capacitance yield greater damping of the voltage ripple.

The transfer behavior under loading by a switched converter is considered in the following. This operating case is illustrated with the example of the HYPERRIDE Aachen demosite's MVDC system section, as shown in Fig. 23. A simplified schematic of the considered system is shown in Fig. 24. The 5 MW DAB constitutes the converter under investigation. Its primary side is fed by the three-level Neutral-Point-Clamped (NPC) MVDC Active Front End (AFE), that is considered to generate voltage perturbations, and therefore represented by the voltage sources V_1 and v_p . The 5 MW DAB's secondary side feeds the modular Medium-Voltage - Low-Voltage (MV/LV) DAB, considered to be operated under constant power transfer. The converters are interconnected by a short cable. The previously analyzed aspects of instabilities, harmonic oscillations and disturbance transfer across the DAB are considered and investigated in the described application case. The system's parameters are listed in Table 3.

Figure 22: Disturbance transfer function of DAB under voltage control for different output capacitances.

Parameter	Value
5 MW DAB input voltage	5 kV
5 MW DAB output voltage	5 kV
5 MW DAB switching frequency	1 kHz
Modular DAB input voltage	5 kV
Modular DAB output voltage	700 V
Modular DAB switching frequency	10 kHz
Input and output capacitances	5 mF
Series inductance	10 μ H
Series resistance	1 m Ω

Table 3: Grid Application Case Parameters

Figure 23: Representation of the converters within the Aachen demosite that are considered in the application case.

Figure 24: Simplified schematic representing the application case.

Figure 25: Transfer function $\frac{V_2}{v_p}$ of the input voltage perturbation to the intermediate DC link voltage.

The resulting transfer behavior from the input voltage perturbation to the DC link voltage V_2 is plotted in Fig. 25. A strong damping of the perturbations is observed, similar to the previously analyzed system's. In comparison to the previous examples, the difference in switching frequency has to be considered. Accordingly, in this application the converter inherent resonance lies at 1 kHz, and the transfer characteristic shifts towards lower frequencies.

The input voltage perturbation to output current transfer function $Y_{tf} = \frac{I_3}{v_p}$ is shown in Fig. 26. The load converter's output current also shows a strong damping of the injected disturbances. The effect of the converters' different switching frequencies becomes evident in the transfer function. At 1 kHz and around 10 kHz the converters' resonant behavior resulting from their switching actions is observed.

Overall, even though the effects of cable and DC link resonance and CPL interact with the switched converter behavior, a stable and sufficiently damped system operation is achieved. Especially the sizing of the DC link capacitors as well as control loop interactions need to be considered in applications. In the case of very low damping, the control schemes of CPLs may require adjustments. Care should be taken, that cable and DC link resonances do not coincide with ripple frequencies inherent to one of the system's converter topologies.

Figure 26: Transfer function $\frac{I_o}{V_p}$ of the input voltage perturbation to the output current.

5 Conclusions

Different causes of instabilities in converter based hybrid AC/DC systems are analyzed and related to the practical aspects of HYPERRIDE. Main focus are negative resistance behavior due to constant power load control, resonances resulting from the interaction with passive components of the grid and voltage quality issues. Together with the presented modeling approaches, the effect of a harmonic firewall is investigated and verified with the help of time-series simulations, starting with non-regulated converter operation. Different operating cases are investigated and conclusions for the DAB's disturbance transfer behavior and characteristics are drawn. Application examples relevant to the HYPERRIDE Aachen demosite are analyzed at last, confirming the previously observed characteristics.

It is concluded that the protection coordination and design have to go hand in hand with the stability investigations of hybrid AC/DC systems to prevent contradictory design choices. Especially the sizing of DC link capacitors and series inductances needs to be coordinated between both fields of system design. The basic underlying causes of harmonic oscillations, control loop interactions and voltage quality issues can be mitigated through careful, proper design measures during system design. Interfacing the DAB to loads that exhibit a behavior close to an ideal voltage source can lead to a limited transfer of output current harmonics if input voltage quality issues are present. The implementation of optimized control schemes limits this disturbance transfer further. Operation of the DAB under voltage control with constant current loading effectively limits the propagation of harmonic oscillations with a strong damping. In practical application cases the cable and load impedance influence the damping of harmonic oscillations to an extent. However, in stable configurations with sufficiently sized DC link capacitances, the effect of the harmonic firewall is close to the case assuming ideal load behavior.

Future work should investigate the presented issues for different control approaches and structures. The investigation of further converter topologies can provide more insight into hybrid AC/DC system design.

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